

Studies on Indian Medicinal Plants : Part XXX¹. New Steroids from *Enhydra fluctuans* Lour^f.

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From the petroleum ether extract of *Enhydra fluctuans* Lour. two new steroids have been isolated besides 4, 22-stigmastadien-3-one. Spectral studies indicated them to be (24*S*)-24-ethyl-5, 22, 25-cholestatrien-3 β -yl stearate (II) and (24*S*)-24-ethyl-4, 22, 25-cholestatrien-3-one (III) confirmed by their preparation from (24*S*)-24-ethyl-5, 22, 25-cholestatrien-3 β -ol (I).

THE isolation of the steroidal components of *Enhydra fluctuans* Lour. (Compositae) has been described in the previous part in the series¹. The structure of a new steroidal trienol, namely, 24-ethyl-5, 22, 25-cholestatrien-3 β -ol (I), m.p. 151°-52°, $[\alpha]_D -44^\circ$, obtained along with stigmasterol (IV) from this plant as well as from *Alangium lamarckii* Thw. (Alangiaceae) has also been published² from this laboratory[†]. We now wish to report the characterization of other new steroids, viz. (24*S*)-24-ethyl-5, 22, 25-cholestatrien-3 β -yl stearate (II), m.p. 99°, $[\alpha]_D -25.5^\circ$, (24*S*)-24-ethyl-4, 22, 25-cholestatrien-3-one (III), m.p. 104°, $[\alpha]_D +72.2^\circ$ and 4, 22-stigmastadien-3-one (V), m.p. 114°, $[\alpha]_D +60^\circ$, encountered in this species.

All the steroids, extracted with petroleum ether, were separated by column chromatography over silica gel. The ketones (III and V) and the alcohols (I and IV) were obtained as intimate mixtures. They however, could eventually be resolved into the components through chromatography over silica gel impregnated with silver nitrate[†].

The stearate II showed strong peaks at 1735, 965 and 880 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum for a carbonyl, a *trans* disubstituted double bond and a terminal methylene function, respectively. The NMR spectrum of the compound integrated for approximately eighty protons and a molecular formula C₄₇H₈₀O₂ would be compatible with the elemental analysis.

† Presented before the Convention of Chemists, Allahabad, October 8-12, 1972.

* In a recent paper, the CIBA group (B. S. Joshi and V. N. Kamat, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 771) also recorded the isolation of this compound from *E. fluctuans*

† Because of their close melting points, optical rotations and *Rf* values, the mixture of the sterols (I and IV) would ordinarily be confused as stigmasterol itself. In silver nitrate impregnated TLC plate, however, the acetates not only show distinct *Rf* values but the colours of the spots developed with Liebermann-Burchardt reagent are also different—blue for I and pink for IV. Moreover, the IR peak at around 880 cm⁻¹ for the additional double bond in the trienol (I) distinguished it from IV.

Though its mass spectrum did not exhibit the molecular ion, the peak at the highest mass range appeared at *m/e* 392 as the base peak and the spectrum thereafter was virtually the same as that of the acetate of I. The apparent facile primary loss of a C₁₈H₃₆O₂ moiety strongly indicated the compound to be a fatty acid ester of I, supported by an intense NMR signal at δ 1.32 and the formation of I in quantitative yield on saponification. The final confirmation of the structure came through its preparation from I on condensation with stearoyl chloride.

The less polar ketone analysed for C₂₉H₄₆O (M⁺ 410). The intense peak at *m/e* 124 found in the mass spectrum is known³ to be characteristic of a Δ^4 -3-keto steroid which was in accord with the UV ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 240 nm, log ϵ 4.26) and IR ($\nu_{\max}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 1675 and 1620 cm⁻¹) spectra. The IR peak at 970 cm⁻¹ also indicated the presence of a *trans* disubstituted double bond in the molecule. The compound was thus inferred to be 4, 22-stigmastadien-3-one (V), confirmed by its direct comparison with a specimen prepared from stigmasterol[†].

The more polar ketone could be formulated as C₂₉H₄₄O (M⁺ 408). The IR evidence for a conjugated carbonyl ($\nu_{\max}$ 1670 and 1615 cm⁻¹), UV maximum at 240 nm (log ϵ 4.24) and the mass spectral peak at *m/e* 124 indicated it to be a Δ^4 -3-keto steroid. The other IR peaks at 970 cm⁻¹ for a *trans* disubstituted double bond and at 1645 and 880 cm⁻¹ for a terminal methylene group showed the presence of two more double bonds in the compound as in I corroborated by its mass spectral fragmentation pattern as in the sequel. It shows a primary loss of an ethyl radical

† Though the IR spectra of the samples were virtually superimposable and no depression in the mixture m.p. was observed, the purest natural sample recorded an m.p. lower by about 10° than the synthetic one. This may be due to the presence of the corresponding dihydro derivative as impurity since the mass spectrum of the natural compound showed an ion peak at *m/e* 412 also. The possibility of its being the 24*S* epimer could not, however, be altogether ruled out.

(*m/e* 379) while the high intensity of the peaks at *m/e* 137 and 109 corresponding to the respective compositions of $C_{10}H_{17}$ and C_8H_{13} (high resolution) would suggest allylic cleavage of conjugated dienes (*a, b*) formed by initial double bond migration (Scheme 1). Simultaneously, charge retention in

β -sitosterol also furnished, besides the expected 4-stigmasten-3-one, m.p. 92°–94°, a compound, m.p. 164°, identified as 4-stigmastene-3, 6-dione [lit.⁵ m.p. 170°–72°] The dione is the major product, when the reaction is run at room temperature with excess reagent, a condition under which cholesterol has

these fragmentations in the remaining part of the molecule would explain the peaks at *m/e* 271 and 299. In addition, the base peak at *m/e* 269, corresponding to the moderately intense peak at *m/e* 271 in the spectrum of $\Delta^5, 22, 3$ -hydroxysteroids could be rationalised⁴ by side chain elimination with transfer of two hydrogens. On the other hand, the spectrum of the dienone (V) can be differentiated by the presence of an intense peak at *m/e* 124 arising by cleavage involving the carbonyl group. Thus, it appears that the presence of two double bonds favours the cleavage in the side chain of the trienone.

The tentative structure III thus assigned to the ketone was finally established by its preparation from I. Jones oxidation of I with slight excess of the reagent also yielded a hitherto unreported compound, m.p. 147°–48°, $[\alpha]_D -64.1^\circ$, in low yield. It absorbed at 250 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.03) in the UV and at 1690, 1675 and 1605 cm^{-1} in IR for an enedione system besides showing peaks for the two double bonds in the side chain. The compound was thus assigned the (24*S*)-24-ethyl-4, 22, 25-cholestatriene-3, 6-dione structure (VI). Under similar conditions

recently been reported⁶ to lead to 4-cholestene-3,6-dione.

As regards the stereochemistry at C-24 of the triene series, we initially suggested² *R* configuration for the trienol (I) based on (i) the difference in physical constants for the sterol and its derivatives with those reported⁷ (Table I) for the 24*S* isomer, and (ii) the close correspondence in the sign and magnitude of the molecular rotation difference between I and the 26-nor-25-one (VIII) with that for the Δ^5 series calculated from the published⁸ data. However, this assignment needed revision consequent on the reversal of the C-24 stereochemistry of 5 α -stigmasta-7, 22, 25-trien-3 β -ol on synthetic⁹ and ORD evidences and the data for synthetic 24*R* isomer (VII) of I being now available¹⁰. The ORD spectrum of our 26-nor-25-one (VIII) also exhibited the same sign as the acetate of synthetic (24*S*)-26-nor-25-one¹⁰, the rotation being somewhat stronger in the positive region (317 nm; +3670°) but almost equal in the negative region (269 nm; -2920°). TLC over silica gel impregnated with silver nitrate as well as GLC of the acetate, of both natural and synthetic sterols

also proved that they are exactly identical. We now, therefore, assign the (24*S*)-24-ethyl-5, 22, 25-cholestatrien-3 β -ol structure to our previously reported stigmasta-5, 22, 25-trien-3 β -ol.

TABLE I. REPORTED PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF 24-ETHYL-5, 22, 25-CHOLESTATRIEN-3 β -OLS AND DERIVATIVES

Structure	C-24 configuration	m.p. (°C)	[α] _D degrees	Acetate		Ref.
				m.p. (°C)	[α] _D degrees	
I	<i>S</i>	151-52	-44.0	149-50	-46.6	2
		146	-37.8	141	—	7
		145.5	-37.6	140	-34.7	11
VII	<i>R</i>	151	-59	131-32	-65	10
VIII	<i>S</i>	167-68	+60.4	—	—	2
		—	—	142	—	7
		—	—	141-42	+48	10
IX	<i>R</i>	—	—	137-38	-158	10

Experimental

Oxidation of β -sitosterol :

To a solution of β -sitosterol (0.2 g.) in acetone (50 ml) Jones reagent¹² (0.3 ml) was added with

stirring at room temperature. The reaction mixture was treated with a drop of methanol and filtered through celite. Evaporation of the solvent left a gummy residue which was repeatedly chromatographed over silica gel columns. Elution with 30-40% benzene in petroleum ether yielded 4-stigmasten-3-one (20 mg), crystallised from aq. alcohol in flakes, m.p. 92°-94°, ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1675, 1610 cm^{-1} ; followed by 4-stigmastene-3,6-dione (20 mg), crystallising out of alcohol also in flakes, m.p. 164°. [lit.⁵, m.p. 170°-72°], ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1675 (br), 1610 cm^{-1} , λ_{max}^{EtOH} 248 nm (log ϵ 4.02).

Oxidation of stigmasterol :

To a stirred slurry of stigmasterol (0.2 g) in acetone (30 ml) at 0° was added Jones reagent (0.3 ml). Work-up by the above procedure and chromatography furnished 4, 22-stigmastadien-3-one (0.09 g), crystallised from acetonitrile in fine needles, m.p. 124°-25°, ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1680, 1615, 970 cm^{-1} .

Oxidation of (24*S*)-24-ethyl-5,22,25-cholestatrien-3 β -ol (I) :

A stirred slurry of I (0.1 g) in acetone (20 ml) at 0° was treated with 0.2 ml of Jones reagent (using half the amount of H₂SO₄). Usual work up followed by chromatography yielded, besides unconverted I

(50 mg) and (24*S*)-24-ethyl-4,22,25-cholestatrien-3-one (25 mg, crystallised from acetonitrile), m.p. 101°-102°, $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 1675, 1645, 1615, 970, 880 cm^{-1} ; (24*S*)-24-ethyl-4,22,25-cholestatriene-3,6-dione (20 mg, crystallised from petroleum ether), m.p. 147°-48°, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 250 nm (log ϵ 4.03), $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1690, 1675, 1645, 1605, 970, 890 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 82.40; H, 10.46%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_2$: C, 82.41; H, 10.02%).

Saponification of (24S)-24-ethyl-5,22,25-cholestatrien-3 β -yl stearate (II):

Hydrolysis of II (130 mg) with 5% alc. KOH yielded quantitatively (24*S*)-24-ethyl-5,22,25-cholestatrien-3 β -ol (I), m.p. 151°-52°, identical in every respect (m.m.p., TLC, IR) with the natural product.

Preparation of (II) from (I):

Acylation of I (20 mg) with two drops of stearoyl chloride in pyridine (2 drops) in the usual way yielded 25 mg of the stearate (II) identical (m.p., m.m.p. and IR) with the natural product.

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